

Isonitrosoacetylacetone and Isonitrosoacetophenone as Extractants and Spectrophotometric Reagents for Iron(II)

U. B. TALWAR & B. C. HALDAR

Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory, Institute of Science, Bombay-32

(Received 14 September, 1970)

HINAA and HINAP have been employed for rapid separation and spectrophotometric determination of iron(II) by extraction into butanol and chloroform respectively. As an extractant and spectrophotometric reagent for Fe(II), HINAP is better than HINAA. The species extracted into butanol and chloroform are $\text{Fe}(\text{INAA})_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{INAP})_2$ respectively. The pK values of the extraction equilibrium constants at 29° are 2.9 ± 0.2 and 3.1 ± 0.3 for the systems $\text{Fe}(\text{II}) \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -HINAA-butanol and $\text{Fe}(\text{II}) \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -HINAP-chloroform respectively.

A large number of reagents for the extraction and colorimetric estimation of traces of iron have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁷ but they have their own limitations. Isonitrosoacetylacetone, $\text{CH}_3\text{COC}(\text{:NOH})\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$, (HINAA) reacts with iron(II) in alkaline solution to produce a blue color which can be used for the detection of microgram amounts of iron(II)⁸. Kröhnke detected as low as 0.03 μg of iron per ml. by extracting the blue colored iron(II)-isonitrosoacetophenone ($\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ -HINAP) complex into chloroform⁹. However, no attempt has been made to utilize HINAA and HINAP, $\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{:NOH})\}$, for the separation and spectrophotometric determination of iron. Considering that these compounds are useful analytical reagents for palladium(II) and nickel(II)¹⁰⁻¹³ their applications have been extended to rapid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Fe(II).

Apparatus and Reagents : Apparatus, activity measurements, reagents, chemicals and the preparations of solutions required for the interference studies are described elsewhere¹³. HINAA and HINAP were prepared by the methods prescribed by Welcher¹⁴. Iron stock solution was prepared by dissolving ferric ammonium sulfate in sulfuric acid and diluting suitably. It was standardised by titrating against potassium dichromate solution¹⁵.

Extraction and separation procedure : An aliquot of iron (50 to 1000 μg) solution taken in a 25 ml. beaker was treated with 0.5 ml of 3 M sodium thiosulfate solution to reduce Fe(III) to Fe(II). 1 ml of 2% aqueous solution of HINAA or 2% alcoholic solution of HINAP was added and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to the required value with sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid, keeping the total volume to 10 ml. The mixture was transferred into a 50 ml separatory funnel and shaken for two minutes with an equal volume of organic solvent. After the separation of the two phases, the pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was measured. An aliquot of each phase was removed and iron was estimated by the thiocyanate method. In some experiments, the extraction of iron(II) was checked by measuring the activity of Fe-59 on a gamma-ray spectrometer. The extractions

of other ions, which were added before adjusting the pH of the solution, were evaluated by using radioisotopes. The separation of iron(II) with HINAA was achieved by extracting with two 5 ml portions of butanol from 10 ml of aqueous phase at pH 7.5. The combined butanol phase was equilibrated twice with 5 ml of 1 M HCl and iron was estimated in the acid phase. In separation experiments with HINAP, iron(II) was extracted from 10 ml of aqueous mixture at pH 8.0 by two equilibrations with 5ml portions of chloroform. It was re-extracted into the aqueous phase by stripping the combined chloroform extracts twice with 5 ml of 1 M HCl and estimated colorimetrically.

Procedure for spectrophotometric determination of iron : Take 1 ml of solution containing 2.0 to 30 μg of Fe, 0.5 ml of 3 M $Na_2S_2O_3$ solution and 1 ml of 1% aqueous solution of HINAA or 1 ml of 1% alcoholic solution of HINAP in a 25-ml beaker. Adjust the pH of the mixture containing HINAA to 7.5 and that containing HINAP to 8.0, maintaining the total volume to 10 ml. Transfer the mixture into a 50-ml separatory funnel. With solution containing HINAA, wash the beaker with 5 ml of butanol and pour the butanol into the separatory funnel. Equilibrate for two minutes and collect the organic extract in a 10-ml measuring flask. Repeat the extraction with 3-ml and 2-ml portions of butanol, collect the organic extracts in the flask and make up the volume up to the mark with butanol. Use chloroform for the mixture solution containing HINAP and follow the procedure employed in the extraction with butanol. Measure absorbance of butanol and chloroform solutions at 590 nm and 650 nm respectively. Calculate the amount of iron from the appropriate curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the extraction of iron(II) as a function of pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase. The extraction of iron(II) into butanol from aqueous solution containing HINAA reaches maximum value (96%) over the pH range 7.3–8.0. In the extraction from aqueous solution containing HINAP, the pH for maximum extraction (99.3%) of iron(II) into chloroform is 7.8–8.5. The maximum amounts of iron(II) extractable into 10 ml of butanol from HINAA solution and into 10 ml of chloroform from HINAP solution are 2 mg and 3 mg respectively. Of the solvents investigated butanol and chloroform offer the best advantages for the systems Fe(II)-HINAA- $Na_2S_2O_3$ and Fe(II)-HINAP- $Na_2S_2O_3$ respectively. The extractions into various solvents give the following series :

Fe(II)-HINAA- $Na_2S_2O_3$ system^a at pH 7.5 :

<i>n</i> -Butanol	>	iso-amyl-alcohol	>	Methyl ethyl ketone	>	Ethyl acetate	>
(24)		(4.7)		(1.4)		(0.25)	
Nitrobenzene	>	Ether	>	Chloroform	>	Carbon tetrachloride	>
(0.06)		(0.0012)		(0.0011)		(0.0004)	(0.0001)

Fe(II)-HINAP- $Na_2S_2O_3$ system^a at pH 8.0 :

Chloroform	~	<i>n</i> -Butanol	>	Benzene	>	Nitrobenzene	>	Iso-amyl alcohol	>
(144.2)		(144.2)		(57.5)		(25.0)		(3.3)	
		Ethyl acetate	>	Methyl ethyl ketone.					
		(1.0)		(0.1)					

^a The extraction coefficient values of Fe(II) are indicated in the parenthesis.

In the extraction from HINAP solution with carbon tetrachloride and ether, insoluble solid separates.

The effects of reducing agents on the extraction of iron(II) from HINAA and HINAP solutions have been studied. Hydroxylamine hydrochloride destroys the blue color due to Fe(II)-isonitrosoacetylacetonate and so the extraction of iron into butanol does not occur. However, it does not interfere in the extraction of Fe(II) with HINAP into

Figure 1 : Extraction of iron at different pH.

⊙—HINAA.

×—HINAP.

chloroform. Stannous chloride, magnesium metal and sodium thiosulfate are equally efficient as reducing agents in the extractions of Fe(II) from HINAA and HINAP solutions into butanol and chloroform respectively. However, with higher concentration of stannous chloride, turbidity or precipitate appears in the aqueous phase. The advantage of using sodium thiosulfate as a reducing agent is that the excess thiosulfate can suppress the extractions of other ions from HINAA solution into butanol and from HINAP solution into chloroform.

Salting out agents such as nitrates of lithium, potassium, barium and calcium do not affect the extractions of Fe(II) in the systems Fe(II)-HINAA- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -butanol and Fe(II)-HINAP- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -chloroform. But the extraction coefficient value of Fe(II) in the system Fe(II)-HINAA- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -butanol is raised from 24.0 to 31.0 by the presence of 0.5 M magnesium nitrate.

The extractions of the following ions into butanol from HINAA solution at pH 7.5 and into chloroform from HINAP solution at pH 8.0 are less than 1% : Cu(II), Cd(II), Cr(III), Ce(III), Sn(IV), Sb(III), Os(VI), Cs(I), W(VI), SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , Mn(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Ag(I) and Cl. Of these ions, the first ten are slightly less extractable into chloroform from HINAP solution at pH 8.0 than into butanol from HINAA solution at pH 7.5. With the remaining ions, the converse is true. Co(II), Ni(II), Hg(II) and Ru(III) are appreciably extracted into butanol from HINAA solution and also into chloroform from

HINAP solution. However, the cobalt extracted into butanol and chloroform remains in the organic phase during the stripping of Fe(II) with 1 *M* HCl, thus permitting the separation of iron(II) from Co(II). In both the systems Fe(II) can be selectively extracted into the organic phase by complexing Co(II) with sulfite, Hg(II) with chloride and Ru(III) with thiourea. In the presence of the complexing agents, not more than 0.5% of these ions accompany Fe(II) into the organic phase. Tartrate masks the extraction of nickel into chloroform from HINAP solution of pH 8 but it is not so effective in reducing the extraction of nickel into butanol from HINAA solution at pH 7.5. The extractions of Re(VII), Ir(IV) and As(V) into chloroform from HINAP solution at pH 8.0 are less than 0.6%, while they are extracted to the extent of 3% or more into butanol from HINAA solution at pH 7.5.

Table 1 summarises the results of separation of Fe(II) from other elements in synthetic mixtures and in gun metal. With synthetic mixtures of iron and 20 mg of copper, cobalt or nickel, the recovery of pure iron free from detectable amounts of other elements is 98%

TABLE 1
Separation of Iron from other Elements

Sample	Composition	Iron recovered		Amounts of other elements in recovered iron
		HINAA	HINAP	
Synthetic mixture	25 μ g of Fe ⁺	25.0	25.0	Not detectable.
	20 mg of Cu.			
„	25 μ g of Fe ⁺	24.5	24.5	„
	20 mg of Co.			
„	25 μ g of Fe ⁺	24.5	24.5	„
	20 mg of Ni.			
Gun metal	0.05% Fe,			„
	86.6% Cu,			
	and small amounts of Sn, Sb, Pb, Ni, P and Si.	0.05%	0.05%	

or better and the time required for the separation is not more than 7 min. When HINAA was used, the separations of Ni(II) and Fe(II) were achieved by the following procedure.

The solution containing 25 μ g of Fe(II) and 10 mg of nickel was treated with 2 ml of 2% HINAA solution. After adjusting the pH of the solution to 7.5, the mixture was extracted thrice with 3 ml of chloroform to remove nickel from the aqueous phase. 1 ml of 1% HINAA was added to the aqueous phase and the pH of the aqueous solution was again adjusted to 7.5 with sodium hydroxide. It was then extracted with 10 ml (5+3+2) of *n*-butanol. The combined butanol was stripped with 10 ml (5+5) of 1 *M* HCl and iron was estimated in the aqueous phase by the thiocyanate method.

100 μ g of Fe(II) can be separated from 10 mg of Fe(III) by extracting 10 ml of aqueous solution containing Fe(II), Fe(III) and HINAP at pH 8.0 with an equal volume of chloroform and washing the chloroform extract once with water at pH 8.0. Fe(II) is stripped from

the organic phase by equilibrations with two 5-ml portions of 1 *M* HCl. The recovery of Fe(II) is almost quantitative and the recovered Fe(II) contains less than 0.1 μg of Fe(III).

Procedure for the separation of iron from other elements in gun metal :

A 10 mg sample of gun metal was dissolved in minimum volume of conc. HCl plus a few drops of conc. HNO_3 added dropwise and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. 1 ml of water was added and the clear solution was treated with 2 ml of 5 *M* sodium thio-sulfate, 2 ml of 5 *M* sodium fluoride and 1 ml of 0.1 *M* sodium tartrate. 2 ml of 5% aqueous solution of HINAA or 5% alcoholic solution of HINAP were added to the solution and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to the required value. Fe(II) was then separated as described above and estimated colorimetrically by the thiocyanate method.

The plot (Figure 2) of $\log E$ vs $\log (\text{HR})_0$, where $(\text{HR})_0$ represents the concentration of HINAP or HINAA in the organic phase, gives a straight line of slope equal to 2, indicating that the extracted species contains iron(II) and HINAP or HINAA in the ratio of 1 : 2.

Figure 2 : Plot of $\log E$ vs. $\text{Log} (\text{HR})_0$.

Concentration of Fe = $4.5 \times 10^{-5} M$.

HINAP	pH
Δ	7.5
\circ	6.9
\odot	5.8
HINAA	
\times ...	7.0
\square	6.6

Extraction data over the pH range 5.8–7.5 seem to indicate that the net extraction equilibria may be represented as follows :

and

$$K_{\text{FeR}_2} = \frac{[\text{FeR}_{2(0)}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^+][\text{HR}]_0^2}$$

Where terms in square brackets denote concentrations and FeR_2 stands for $\text{Fe}(\text{INAP})_2$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{INAA})_2$. The values of $\text{p}K_{\text{Fe}(\text{INAP})_2}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{Fe}(\text{INAA})_2}$ at 29° are 3.1 ± 0.3 and 2.9 ± 0.2 respectively.

Absorption spectrum (A in Figure 3) of the color extracted into butanol from Fe(II)-HINAA- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution exhibits a strong band near 590 nm ($\epsilon = 26,540$) while that (B in Figure 3) of the color extracted from aqueous solution of Fe(II)-HINAP- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ reveals two intense maxima at 610 nm ($\epsilon = 29,640$) and 650 nm ($\epsilon = 30,650$). The solvents

Figure 3 : Absorption spectra of iron(II)-isonitrosoacetylacetonate and of iron(II)-isonitrosoacetophenone

(A) $\text{Fe} = 1.43 \times 10^{-5}M$, $\text{HINAA} = 7.75 \times 10^{-3}M$, $\text{pH} = 7.5$.

(B) $\text{Fe} = 2.86 \times 10^{-5}$, $\text{HINAP} = 7.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $\text{pH} = 8.0$.

equilibrated with the aqueous solution containing all the reactants except iron do not show absorptions at these wavelengths. The colors in butanol and chloroform solutions measured at 590 nm and 650 nm respectively obey Beer's law in the range 0.2 to 3.0 μg of iron per ml. The intensity of the color in the organic phase remains unaffected by the variations of the concentrations of HINAA or HINAP from 0.5 to 10%, and thiosulfate from 0.1 to 1.5 M , temperature from 7° to 35° and equilibration time over the period 2 to 30 min. The blue color extracted into chloroform from HINAP solution is stable for a longer period (10 hr) than that extracted into butanol from HINAA solution (6 hr). HINAP in NaOH solution is as efficient as alcoholic solution of HINAP in the extraction of Fe(II) into chloroform.

U(VI), V(V), Pb(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Sr(II), Ti(IV), Li(I), Mg(II), SCN^- , NO_3^- , Br^- , I^- , F^- , S^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, Ac^- , BrO_3^- , thiourea and the ions, which have already been reported to extract into butanol and chloroform to the extent of 1% or less, do not interfere colorimetrically when present in milligram amounts. Cyanide does not interfere when Fe(II) is extracted into chloroform from HINAP solution but it causes serious interference in the

extraction of Fe(II) into butanol from HINAA solution. Though the extractions of As(V) and Re(VII) into butanol from HINAA solution are 8.3% and 6% respectively, their presence in the organic phase do not affect the results of iron estimation. If Au(III) is complexed with thiourea and Hg(II) with chloride prior to the extraction of Fe(II) into the organic solvent then they can be tolerated in mg amounts. The interference by oxalate is removed by extracting Fe(II) into the organic phase in the presence of sodium molybdate. EDTA does not interfere in the estimation of Fe(II) with HINAP but it does when HINAA is used. The extraction of Fe(II) into butanol from HINAA solution containing Cu(II) and excess sodium thiosulfate is free from the interference by EDTA. Zr(IV) and Sn(II), though they do not interfere, are kept in solution by adding sodium fluoride.

Iron was determined in gun metal by preparing the solution as described earlier and processing the solution as per recommended procedure for spectrophotometric determinations of Fe(II) with HINAA and HINAP. The results (Table 2) are in excellent agreement with the reported values.

TABLE 2

Precision and Accuracy of the Methods for the Determination of Iron with HINAA and HINAP

Sample	Reagent	No. of replicate analysis	Amount of iron taken (μg)	95% limit for the average (μg)
Iron solution	HINAA	10	10	9.96 ± 0.20
Iron solution	HINAP	10	17	16.80 ± 0.30
Gun metal (10 mg)	HINAA	2	5.0	4.9 ^a
Gun metal (10 mg)	HINAP	2	5.0	5.0 ^a

^a Average of two determinations.

The main advantages of the methods proposed are that the extractions of Fe(II) into butanol from $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -HINAA solution at pH 7.5 and into chloroform from $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ -HINAP solution at pH 8.0 permit rapid separation and spectrophotometric determination of iron. Microgram amounts of Fe(II) can be separated from milligram quantities of Fe(III) by extraction with chloroform from aqueous HINAP solution at pH 8.0 and as much as 3 mg of Fe(II) can be extracted by 10 ml of chloroform. HINAP is a better reagent than HINAA for the separation and spectrophotometric determination of iron.

This work was supported by a P.L.480 grant sponsored by the U.S. National Bureau of Standards.

REFERENCES

1. G. H. Morrison and H. Freiser, *Solvent Extraction in Analytical Chemistry*, John Wiley and Sons, N.Y., 1957.
2. E. B. Sandell, *Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals*, Interscience Publ., New York, 1959.

3. F. P. Dwyer and N. A. Gibson, *Analyst*, 1951, **76**, 548.
4. A. B. Beck, *Aust. J. Expt. Biol. Med. Sc.*, 1945, **23**, 311.
5. E. M. Penner and W. R. Inman, *Talanta*, 1962, **9**, 1027.
6. A. M. Poskenzer and B. M. Foreman, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **16**, 323.
7. R. J. Lacoste, M. R. Earing and S. E. Wiberly, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 871.
8. W. Kuster, *Z. physik. chem.*, 1926, **155**, 157.
9. E. Kröhnke, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 527.
10. U. B. Talwar and B. C. Haldar, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 1929.
11. U. B. Talwar and B. C. Haldar, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1967, **39**, 264.
12. U. B. Talwar and B. C. Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 803.
13. U. B. Talwar and B. C. Haldar, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1970, **51**, 53.
14. F. J. Welcher, *Organic Analytical Reagents*, Vol. II, Van Nostrand, New York, 1955 pp. 275, 280.
15. A. I. Vogel, *Text Book of Quantitative Analysis*, Longmans Green, London, 1962.